

MOST READED PAPERS

**International Journal of Software
Engineering & Applications (IJSEA)**

ISSN : 0975 - 9018 (Online); 0976-2221 (Print)

<http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/ijsea.html>

A RELIABLE AND AN EFFICIENT WEB TESTING SYSTEM

Kamran Ali and Xia Xiaoling

School of Computer Science and Technology, Donghua University,

Songjiang District, Shanghai 201620 – China

ABSTRACT

To improve the reliability and efficiency of Web Software, the Testing Team should be creative and innovative, the experience and intuition of Tester also matters a lot. And most often the destructive nature of Tester brings reliable software to the user. Actually, Testing is the responsibility of everybody who is involved in the Project. But, one's personal curiosity and attention is more important than the various techniques and tools available in the market for Web Testing due to the phenomena that Software Testing is an art. In this study, we are actually discussing certain techniques and tools which can be helpful to minimize bugs in Web Application and achieve reliability and efficiency to a certain level. Indeed, for bettering the quality of Web Application, Testing may not be considered as the only effective method because no one can certify that a system is bug-free. This paper presents some essential web testing techniques, strategies, methods and tools which need to be focused on when performing Web Testing for several web applications in order to achieve better results.

KEYWORDS

Web Testing, Web Software, Reliability, Efficiency, Software Engineering.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V10N1/10119ijsea01.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] [R Chopra - 2018 - Stylus Publishing, LLC "Software Testing a Self-Teaching Introduction"](#).
- [2] YL Li, YN Zhang, GX Zhao, SN Zhao - US Patent 9,703,694, 2017 - Google Patents, "Techniques for testing software".
- [3] R Kaser, J Bruno, D Timberlake - US Patent App. 15/238,034, 2018 - Google Patents "[Systems and methods for software testing and test management.](#)"
- [4] G.A. Di Lucca, A.R. Fasolino , 1186 "[Testing Web-based Applications: The state of the art and future trends](#)" Information and Software Technology 48 (2006)
- [5] A April, CY Laporte – 2018, Software quality assurance
- [6] GS Walia, JC Carver – "[A systematic literature review to identify and classify software requirement errors](#)" Information and Software Technology, 2009 – Elsevier
- [7] Journal of Systems and Software, Volume 91, May 2014, Pages 174-201, Web application testing: A systematic literature review.
- [8] F Dalpiaz, A Ferrari, X Franch, C Palomares, [Natural Language Processing for Requirements Engineering:The Best Is Yet to Come](#), - IEEE Software, 2018 –
- [9] Arora A., and Sinha M, "[Web Application Testing: A Review on Techniques, Tools and State of Art](#)" International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 3, Issue 2, February-2012 ISSN 2229-5518
- [10] Dheeraj kakaraparthi, "[An overview and analysis of automated testing tools: Ranorex, Test complete, Selenium](#)" International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) e-ISSN: 2395- 006, pISSN: 2395-0072, Volume: 04 Issue: 10 | Oct -2017.
- [11] Yuan-FangLiParamjit K.DasDavid L.Dowe, Two decades of Web application testing—A survey of recent advances, Information Systems, Volume 43, July 2014, Pages 20-54
- [12] Mohamed Monier Information System Department, Faculty of Computers and Informatics, Zagazig University, Egypt, "[Evaluation of automated web testing tools](#)" International Journal of Computer Applications Technology and Research Volume 4– Issue 5, 405 - 408, 2015, ISSN:- 2319–8656,
- [13] JeffTian*LiMa, "Web Testing for Reliability Improvement." Advances in Computers, Volume 67, 2006, Pages 177-224,

- [14] Ian Sommerville: Software Engineering (10th Edition)
- [15] Software Quality: Concepts and Practice, 1st, Wiley-IEEE Computer Society Pr ©2018
- [16] Tamai, T Anzai, [Quality Requirements Analysis with Machine Learning](#) - ENASE, 2018 –
- [17] P Achimugu, A Selamat, R Ibrahim, A systematic literature review of software requirements prioritization research, - Information and software technology, 2014 – Elsevier.
- [18] W Hu, JC Carver, GS Walia “[Development of a human error taxonomy for software requirements: a systematic literature review](#)” Anu, ... - Information and Software ..., 2018 – Elsevier
- [19] US Shah, DC Jinwala - “[Resolving ambiguities in natural language software requirements: a comprehensive survey](#)” ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes, 2015
- [20] JW Wing - 2017 - 196.21.61.18, “[On improving the understanding of software requirements by clients](#)”
- [21] H Schoenmakers, RJ Kusters, “[Factors that Complicate the Selection of Software Requirements: Validating Factors from Literature in an Empirical Study](#)”, Conference on Software, 2018
- [22] T Diamantopoulos, M Roth, a Symeonidis “[Software requirements as an application domain for natural language processing](#)” Language Resources, 2017 – Springer
- [23] A Hussain, EOC Mkpojiogu, “[Requirements: Towards an understanding on "why software projects fail"](#)”, AIP Conference Proceedings, 2016
- [24] S Schneider Wollersheim, H Krcmar “[How do requirements evolve over time? A case study investigating the role of context and experiences in the evolution of enterprise software requirements](#)” - Journal of Information, 2018 – Springer
- [25] Software Engineering: A Practitioner's Approach By Roger S. Pressman
- [26] “[Alignment of Requirements Specification and Testing: A Systematic Mapping Study](#)”, 2011 IEEE Fourth International Conference on Software Testing, Verification and Validation
- [27] Requirements engineering for software and system PA Laplante – 2017.

- [28] Rapid quality assurance with Requirements Smells, Journal of Systems and Software Volume 123, January 2017, Pages 190-213.
- [29] The application of knowledge management to software evolution, International Journal of Information Management Volume 37, Issue 1, Part A, February 2017, Pages 1499-1506.
- [30] T Diamantopoulos, M Roth, a Simonides “[Software requirements as an application domain for natural language processing](#)” Language Resources, 2017 – Springer
- [31] P Heck, A Zaidman –“[A systematic literature review on quality criteria for agile requirements specifications](#)” Software Quality Journal, 2018 – Springer

APPLYING CONTINUOUS INTEGRATION FOR INCREASING THE MAINTENANCE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF WEB APP

Sen-Tarng Lai, Shih Chien University, Taiwan

ABSTRACT

In order to project resource management and time control, software system needs to be decomposed into subsystems, functional modules and basis components. Finally, all tested components have to integrate to be the complete system. Applying IID (Iterative Incremental Development) mechanism, agile development model becomes the practical method to reduce software project failure rate. Continuous integration (CI) is an IID implementation concept which can effectively reduce software development risk. Web app with high change characteristic is suitable to use agile development model as the development and maintenance methodology. The paper depth surveys CI operating environment and advantages. Introducing CI concept can make up the moving target problems to impact of Web app. For this, the paper proposes a Continuous Integration based Web Applications Maintenance Procedure (CIWAMP) to assist the system integration operating. Based on CI characteristics, CIWAMP makes Web app can be deployed quickly, increase stakeholder communication frequency, improve staff morale, and effectively reduce Web app maintenance quality and efficiency.

KEYWORDS

Continuous Integration, agile process, Web app, integration test, maintenance quality and efficiency

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V10N1/10119ijsea03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Brandon, D. M. (Ed.). Software Engineering for Modern Web Applications: Methodologies and Technologies, IGI Global, 2008.
- [2] Al-Fedaghi, S., “[Developing Web Applications](#),” International Journal of Software Engineering and Its Applications, Vol. 5 No. 2, April, 2011, pp.57-68.
- [3] Boehm, B.W., “[Software risk management: Principles and practices](#),” IEEE Software, vol. 8, no.1, 1991, pp.32-41.
- [4] Fairley, R., “[Risk management for Software Projects](#),” IEEE Software, vol. 11, no. 3, 1994, pp. 57-67.
- [5] Larman, C. and Basili, V. R., “Iterative and Incremental Development: A Brief History”, Computer, IEEE CS Press, 2004, pp. 48.<https://www.cs.umd.edu/~basili/publications/journals/J90.pdf>
- [6] Schach, S. R., Object-Oriented and Classical Software Engineering, Eighth Edition, McGraw-Hill, New York, 2011.
- [7] Robert C. Martin, Agile Software Development, Principles, Practices and Patterns, Prentice Hall, 2002.
- [8] Szalvay, V., An Introduction to Agile Software Development, CollabNet, Inc., 2004.
- [9] Sthl, D., Mrtensson, T., & Bosch, J., The continuity of continuous integration. Journal of Systems and Software, 127(C), 2017, 150-167.
- [10] Shahin, M., Babar, M. A., & Zhu, L., [Continuous integration, delivery and deployment: a systematic review on approaches, tools, challenges and practices](#). IEEE Access, 5, 2017, 3909-3943.
- [11] Fowler, Martin, “Continuous Integration,” martinfowler.com, <http://www.martinfowler.com/articles/continuousIntegration.html> (1 May 2006).accessed Nov. 9, 2018
- [12] Duvall, Paul, Continuous Integration Servers and Tools, DZone Refcardz. <https://dzone.com/refcardz/continuous-integration-servers#>, (accessed Nov. 11, 2018)
- [13] Duvall, Paul, Matyas, Steve and Glover, Andrew, Continuous Integration: Improving Software Quality and Reducing Risk, Pearson Education, Inc., 2007.
- [14] Booch, Grady, Object-Oriented Analysis and Design with applications 2nd edition, Addison Wesley Longman1994.

- [15] Beck, K. "[Extreme programming: A humanistic discipline of software development](#)," Fundamental Approaches to Software Engineering, 2006, pp. 1-6,
- [16] Crispin, Lisa and House, Tip, "[Testing Extreme Programming](#)", Addison Wesley, 2003.
- [17] Beck, K. Test-Driven Development: By Example, Addison-Wesley, 2003.
- [18] North, Dan, "Introducing BDD," <http://dannorth.net/introducing-bdd/> (accessed Nov. 9, 2018)
- [19] Bavota, G., et al. "[Using structural and semantic measures to improve software modularization](#)," Empirical Software Engineering vol. 18 no. 5, 2013, pp.901-932.
- [20] Saff D. and Erns, M. D., "[Reducing Wasted Development Time via Continuous Testing](#)," Proceeding of IEEE International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE), 2003, pp.281-292.
- [21] Wells, Don "Code the Unit Test First", <http://www.extremeprogramming.org/rules/testfirst.html> (accessed Nov. 9, 2018)
- [22] Cheon, Y. and Leavens, G. T., [A simple and practical approach to unit testing: The JML and JUnit way](#). In European Conference on Object-Oriented Programming, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2002. pp. 231-255
- [23] Fenton, N. E., Software Metrics - A Rigorous Approach, Chapman & Hall, 1991.
- [24] Galin, D., Software Quality Assurance – From theory to implementation, Pearson Education Limited, England, 2004.
- [25] Loeliger, J., and McCullough M., Version Control with Git: Powerful tools and techniques for collaborative software development, O'Reilly Media, Inc., 2012.
- [26] Fowler, Martin, "[Refactoring Improving The Design Of Existing Code](#)," Addison-Wesley, 1999.

AN ITERATIVE HYBRID AGILE METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING ARCHIVING SYSTEMS

Khaled Ebrahim Almajed, Walaa Medhat and Tarek El-Shishtaw

Benha University, Egypt

ABSTRACT

With the massive growth of the organizations files, the needs for archiving system become a must. A lot of time is consumed in collecting requirements from the organization to build an archiving system. Sometimes the system does not meet the organization needs. This paper proposes a domain-based requirement engineering system that efficiently and effectively develops different archiving systems based on new suggested technique that merges the two best used agile methodologies: extreme programming (XP) and SCRUM. The technique is tested on a real case study. The results shows that the time and effort consumed during analyzing and designing the archiving systems decreased significantly. The proposed methodology also reduces the system errors that may happen at the early stages of the development of the system.

KEYWORDS

Requirement Engineering (RE), Agile, SDLC, Extreme Programming (XP), SCRUM, Archiving.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V10N1/10119ijsea02.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Nuseibeh, B.; Easterbrook, S. Requirements engineering: a roadmap. [ICSE'00. Proceedings of the conference on the future of Software engineering. pp. 35–46, 2000.](#)
- [2] Kotonya, Gerald; Sommerville, Ian (September 1998). Requirements Engineering: Processes and Techniques. John Wiley & Sons, 1998.
- [3] Chemuturi, M. (2013). Requirements Engineering and Management for Software Development Projects, 2013.
- [4] Sriram, RandMathew, [S.K Global Software Development Using Agile Methodologies: A Review of Literature.](#) 2012 IEEE International Conference on Management of Innovation and Technology, Bali, 2012.
- [5] Medhat, W, Fouad, KM, Yousef, AH, and Moawad, IF, [published in 12th international conference of Computer Engineering and Systems \(ICCES\), 2017](#)
- [6] ManjulGuptaa, Joey F. Georgeb, andWeidongXiaa, “[Relationships between IT department culture and agile software development practices: An empirical investigation](#)”, “International Journal of Information Management44 (2019) 13–24”, 2019.
- [7] Pacheco, C., and Garcia, I. [A systematic literature review of stakeholder identification methods in requirements elicitation.](#) Journal of Systems and Software, 85(9), 2171-2181, 2012.
- [8] Amani Mahdi Mohammed, Hisham Mohamed Abushama, “[Popular Agile Approaches in Software Development: Review and Analysis](#)”, Researchgate Conference Paper • August 2013.
- [9] Shen, H., Wall, B., Zaremba, M., Chen, Y., & Browne, J. [Integration of business modelling methods for enterprise information system analysis and user requirements gathering.](#) Computers in Industry, 54(3), 307-323, 2014.
- [10] Mohammad Almseidin, Khaled Alrfou², Nidal Alnidami³ and Ahmed Tarawneh, “[A Comparative Study of Agile Methods: XP versus SCRUM](#)”, International Journal of Computer Science and Software Engineering (IJCSSE), Volume 4, Issue 5, May 2015
- [11] Khaleel, Y., Abuhamdah, A., Sara, M. A., & Al-Tamimi, B. [Components and Analysis Method of Enterprise Resource Planning \(ERP\) Requirements in Small and Medium Enterprises \(SMEs\).](#) International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering, 6(2), 682, 2016.
- [12] Farrukh Musa, and Muhammad Ali Tariq, “[Agile Methodology: Hybrid Approach Scrum and XP](#)”, International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 8, Issue 4, April-2017.
- [13] Ankita Sharma, and Manav Bali, “[Comparative Study on Software Development Methods: Agile vs Scrum](#)”, International Journal of Emerging Research in Management &Technology, June 2017.
- [14] Apoorva Singh and Dharendra Pandey, “[Implementation of Requirement Engineering in Extreme Programing and SCRUM](#)”, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science Volume 8, No. 5, May – June 2017.

- [15] Sara Ashraf, Shabib Aftab, "[Scrum with the Spices of Agile Family: A Systematic Mapping](#)", I.J. Modern Education and Computer Science, 2017.
- [16] Julio Cesar Pereira, and Rosaria de F. S. M. Russo, "[Design Thinking Integrated in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review](#)", "international Conference on Project Management / HCist– International Conference on Health and Social Care Information Systems and Technologies",2018.
- [17] Sultania, A. K. (2015, February). [Developing software product and test automation software using Agile methodology](#). In Proceedings of the 2015 Third International Conference on Computer, Communication, Control and Information Technology (C3IT) (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [18] Kniberg, H. (2015). Scrum and XP from the Trenches. [Lulu.com](#).
- [19] Kevin Thompson, Ph.D. "How to Estimate Capacity for Work in Agile Teams", 2012.

INTRODUCING REFINED AGILE MODEL (RAM) IN THE CONTEXT OF BANGLADESH'S SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT ENVIRONMENT CONCENTRATING ON THE IMPROVEMENT OF REQUIREMENT ENGINEERING PROCESS

Nirjhor Anjum¹ and Anwarul Kabir²,

¹REVE Systems, Bangladesh and ²American International University, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

The Software Companies of Bangladesh are using different types of agile models for software development. Although theoretically these models are worthy for small and medium projects, in practical case they are not so effective. In doing so, this paper tries to find out why do the agile models not suitable for Bangladesh's Software Companies and how do the problems that the Software Companies face for using the models can be solved. To reveal the answers, this study is based on survey and interview methods. Findings of this paper show that Bangladesh's Software Companies are facing different problems for implementing traditional agile models, such as, Communicational gap, lack of Documentation, unavailability of Prototype, Customer's lack of knowledge in the area of IT and many more. The study shows that if the Requirement Engineering Process is perfectly managed and some rules are modified in the traditional agile models, these problems can be solved. In doing so, a new model has been proposed by the study named Refined Agile Model (RAM) which is claimed to be better for Bangladesh rather than the traditional Agile Models. This model proposes a process flow which consists of Prototyping Cycle, Development Iteration Cycle and Additional Development Iteration Cycle. This new model also ensures a Requirement Engineer at Client End, sufficient documentation, preparation of prototype and presentation of frequent Demos. After ensuring these requirements in several real time projects, it was found that those projects were completed more effectively compared to all other old project experiences. Eventually, the paper concludes by mentioning that the Refined Agile Model (RAM) is the best model in the Bangladeshi software environment.

KEYWORDS

Agile methodology, Requirement engineering process, Software development life cycle.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V10N4/10419ijsea02.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Moretaza, T. (2016) Ensuring priority for local Software Companies first challenge. The Independent.[Online] 27th June. p.14. Available from: <http://www.theindependentbd.com/post/49371>. [Accessed:03rd July 2016].
- [2] BASIS (2016) BASIS Members Directory 2016. [Online] Available from: http://www.basis.org.bd/index.php/members_area. [Accessed: 28th July 2016].
- [3] A. Tiwana, and M. Keil, “[The one minute risk assessment tool](#),” Communications of the ACM, 2004.
- [4] M. Ben-Menachem, Software Configuration Management Guidebook, McGraw-Hill International (UK) Limited, 1994.
- [5] C. Jones, Software Engineering Best Practices: Lessons from Successful Projects in the Top Companies, McGraw-Hill Osborne Media, 1st ed., 2009.
- [6] K. Wiegers, Software Requirements, Microsoft Press. 1999.
- [7] M. Sudhakar. Managing the Impact of Requirements Volatility. Master Thesis. Department of Computing Science, Umeå University, Umeå, Sweden. 2005.
- [8] V. Rajlich, “[Changing the paradigm of software engineering](#),” Communications of the ACM, vol. 49, no. 8, August 2006.
- [9] Costello, R. and Liu, D. (1995), “[Metrics for Requirements Engineering](#)”: Journal of Systems and Software, Vol 29 (No. 1), pp. 39-63 MIL-STD-498. 1994. Software
- [10] Development and Documentation. U.S. DoD.
- [11] T. JavedManzil, M. Quiser, and S. Durrani, “[A study to investigate the Impact of requirements Instability on Software Defects](#)”, ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes, 29 (3), May 2004, pp:1-7.
- [12] Zowghi, N. Nurmuliani, [A study of the Impact of requirements volatility on Software Project Performance](#), Proceedings of the Ninth Asia-Pacific Software Engineering
- [13] Conference , APSEC 2002, Gold Cost, Queensland, Australia,04-06 Dec 2002, pp:3-11.
- [14] Lamsweerde, A. Requirements Engineering in the Year 00: A research perspective. [In proceeding of the 22nd International conference on Software Engineering \(ICSE'2000\), Limerick, Ireland, 5-19, ACM Press.](#)

BROKE-IMPLEMENT AGILE METHOD OF MOBILE APP DEVELOPMENT

Leena Bhatia¹ and Bindu Jain²,

¹S.S. Jain Subodh P.G. College, India and ²University of Rajasthan, India

ABSTRACT

The mobile application market has been expanding very rapidly. For successful mobile app development and ensuring app's visibility, one needs to follow a systematic approach. Currently, all the models are based on two methodologies of mobile app development i.e. Waterfall methodology and Agile Methodology. In agile methodology, the different phases of app development cycle take place in parallel, with a defined pipeline of expected features and requirements. While there are many advantages of parallel development of various modules under the agile theory, the development is fraught with certain challenges. In a case a previous module doesn't perform as expected, the entire undertaking may be subject to failure. Keeping this weakness in mind, this paper is presenting an idea of broke-implement agile method. This method is especially beneficial from a user's point of view as it provides them the opportunity to customize the app while development is underway. Thus, it helps make the user comfortable and ensure he/ she is satisfied with the product. Moreover, this method helps user choose only the relevant features thereby translating into cost and time savings.

KEYWORDS

Broke-implement, Agile, Waterfall, Google Wave

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V10N3/10319ijsea01.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Afaq Hyder Chohan, Haryanti Mohd Affandi, Jihad Awad and Adi Irfan Che-Ani!!" developed a methododology to Develop a Mobile Application Model to Appraise Housing Design Quality (<https://online-journals.org/index.php/i-jim/article/view/6379>)
- [2] Bhatia, Leena & Jain, Bindu. (2013). Card bases payment mode - an accounting perspective: a comparison between credit card and debit card payment systems in India. Int. J. of Managerial and Financial Accounting. 5. 33 - 44. [10.1504/IJMFA.2013.052408](https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMFA.2013.052408).
- [3] Chaitanya Kaul and Saurav Verma (2015), [A Review Paper on Cross Platform Mobile Application Development IDE](#), IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSR-JCE) e-ISSN: 2278-0661,p-ISSN: 2278-8727, Volume 17, Issue 1, , 30-33
- [4] Chwaber, K. 2004. Agile Project Management with Scrum, Microsoft Press
- [5] Ghislain Edgard MBAYEN MBAYEN (2013) A Mobile Application Development Strategy-Finding Model, <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:679331/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- [6] <https://appinventiv.com/blog/agile-or-waterfall-which-is-the-right-mobile-app-development-approach>
- [7] <https://blog.placeit.net/apps-fail-teach-us-app-marketing/>
- [8] <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:679331/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- [9] <https://mashable.com/2009/05/31/google-wave-features/#tKyo2QGPzqq2>
- [10] <http://www.mountangoatsoftware.com/agile/scrum>
- [11] <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/getting-started-with/9781449379896/ch01.html>
- [12] <https://www.statista.com/statistics/330695/number-of-smartphone-users-worldwide>
- [13] Minh Huynh and Prashant Ghimire (2017), [BROWSER APP APPROACH: CAN IT BE AN ANSWER TO THE CHALLENGES IN CROSS-PLATFORM APP DEVELOPMENT?](#) Journal of Information Technology Eductation: Innovations in Practice Vol:16, 47-68
- [14] Ozturk, Yunus. (2017). Development of a Model for Simple Educational Mobile Applications: A Case Study of Evaluation Matrix.

MOBILE APPLICATION DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGIES ADOPTED IN OMANI MARKET: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Serein Al-Ratrout¹, Omar Husain Tarawneh¹, Moath Husni Altarawneh² and Mejhem Yosef Altarawneh²,

1Al zahra College for Women, Oman and 2The World Islamic Sciences and Education University, Jordan

ABSTRACT

Popularity of mobile phones and huge growing for mobile applications make developers in need for flexible software process, which can deal with many challenges facing the mobile app development process. These challenges include: volatility of requirements, strong user involvement, development time tightness, process simplicity, and production of valuable software in low cost. This research study investigates the current mobile app development approaches adopted in Omani market and provides a comparison between existing methods. The results reveal that Agile approach is the most popular model for mobile software engineering in Omani, as it naturally fits most of the applications required in this market. The study also discusses various agile process models such as Scrum, XP, Lean, DSDM, and others. It is concluded that XP model is the most preferable model used by Omani developers due to its dynamic and adaptive nature for different mobile app processes. The study provides also a series of recommendations for mobile app developers which should help in selecting the most appropriate method that suits the targeted market sector.

KEYWORDS

Development approach, Mobile application, Agile, XP, survey, Oman

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V10N2/10219ijsea02.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Ajit Kumar, K.T. Hari Krishna , Prof. Manjula R, ” [Challenges and Best Practices in Mobile Application Development](#)”, Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR), Vol-2, Issue-12, 2016
- [2] Naila Kousar, Muhammad Sheraz, Aramghan Sarwar, Burhan Mohy-ud-din, Ayesha Shahid, “[Software Engineering: Challenges and their Solution in Mobile App Development](#)”, (IJACSA) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol. 9, No. 1, 2018.
- [3] Anthony I. Wasserman, “[Software Engineering Issues for Mobile Application Development](#)” Proceedings of the Workshop on Future of Software Engineering Research (FoSER), at the 18th ACM, 2010.
- [4] Luis Corral, Alberto Sillitti, Giancarlo Succi, “[Software Development Processes for Mobile Systems, Is Agile Really Taking Over the Business?](#)” 1st International Workshop on the Engineering of Mobile-Enabled Systems (MOBS), 2013.
- [5] V. Rahmimian and R. Ramsin, “[Designing an Agile Methodology for Mobile Software Development: A hybrid Method Engineering Approach](#)”, in proceedings of second international conference on Research Challenges in Information Science, RCIS (2008). Marrakech, 2008, pp. 337- 342.
- [6] A.C. Spataru, “[Agile Development Methods for Mobile Applications](#)”, PhD Thesis, University of Edinburgh, the University Of Edinburg, Edinburg, 2010.
- [7] Giner Alor-ernández, Viviana Yarel Rosales-Morales, and Luis Omar Colombo-Mendoza, “[Frameworks, Methodologies, and Tools for Developing Rich Internet Applications](#)”, Information Science Reference, an imprint of IGI Global, 2015.
- [8] Anureet Kaur, “[Review on Agile Approach to Mobile Application Development](#)”, International Journal of Computing and Technology, Volume 3, Issue 4, April 2016.
- [9] Ali Mesbah ; Philippe Kruchten, “[Real Challenges in Mobile App Development. Mona Erfani Joorabchi](#) “, ACM/IEEE International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement (ESEM), 2013.
- [10] Mudasir M Kirmani, “[Agile Methods for Mobile Application Gevelopment: A comparative analysis](#)”, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science, Volume 8, No. 5, May-June 2017.
- [11] Jalal Shah, Nazri Kama and Nur Azaliah A Bakar, “[A Novel Effort Estimation Model For Software Requirement Changes During Software Development Phase](#)”, International Journal of Software Engineering & Applications (IJSEA), Vol.9, No.6, November 2018

- [12] Ganesh Prasad P, R Hamsini, Smitha G R, “[Agile Development Methodology and Testing for Mobile Applications - A Survey](#)”, International Journal of New Technology and Research (IJNTR), ISSN:2454-4116,Volume-2, Issue-9, September 2016 Pages 98-101
- [13] Sayed Jafar Naqvi, Hahed Al-Shihi, “[Factors Affecting M-commerce Adoption in Oman using Technology Acceptance Modeling Approach](#)”, TEM Journal – Volume 3, Nov-2014.
- [14] Mohamed Sarrab, Ibtisam Al Shibli, and Nabeela Badursha, “[An Empirical Study of Factors Driving the Adoption of Mobile Learning in Omani Higher Education](#)”, International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning, Volume 17, Number 4, June-2016
- [15] Rakesh Belwal, Shweta Belwa, “[Mobile Phone Usage Behavior of University Students in Oman](#)”, International Conference on New Trends in Information and Service Science, NISS '09. International Conference , 2009.
- [16] Harleen K. Flora, Swati V. Chande, Xiaofeng Wang, “[Adopting an Agile Approach for the Development of Mobile Applications](#)”, International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 94 – No.17, May 2014.
- [17] Shakira Banu Kaleel, Ssowjanya HariShankar, “[Applying Agile Methodology in Mobile Software Engineering: Android Application Development and its Challenges](#)”, computer science Technical Report , 2013.
- [18] Ramón Ventura Roque Hernández, Juan Antonio Herrera Izaguirre, Adán López Mendoza, Juan Manuel Salinas Escandón, “[A Practical Approach to the Agile Development of Mobile Apps in the Classroom](#)”, Innovación Educativa, ISSN: 1665-2673 vol. 17, número 73 | enero-abril, 2017.
- [19] Farrukh Musa, Muhammad Ali Tariq, “[Agile Methodology: Hybrid Approach Scrum and XP](#)”, International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 8, Issue 4, April-2017.
- [20] Anitha Ashishdeep, Jitendra Bhatia, Krunal Varma, “[Software Process Models for Mobile Application Development: A Review](#)”, IJCSC volume 7, 2016.
- [21] Thiago Ferraz V. da Cunha, Valeria L. L. Dantas, Rossana M. C. Andrade, “[SLeSS: A Scrum and Lean Six Sigma Integration Approach for the Development of Software Customization for Mobile Phones](#) ”, Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering, 2011.

- [22] Raoul Vallon*, Lukas Wenzel, Martin E. Brüggemann, Thomas Grechenig, “[An Agile and Lean Process Model for Mobile App Development: Case Study into Austrian Industry](#)”, Journal of Software, Volume 10, Number 11, November 2015.
- [23] V. M. M. Thilak , S. R. Devadasan, and N. M. Sivaram, “[A Literature Review on the Progression of Agile Manufacturing Paradigm and Its Scope of Application in Pump Industry](#)”, ScientificWorldJournal, 2015
- [24] Harleen K. Flora , Dr. Swati V. Chande2, “ [A Review and Analysis on Mobile Application Development Process Using Agile Methodologies](#)” , International Journal of Research in Computer Science, Volume 3 Issue 4 (2013)

AGILE PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN NON-SOFTWARE SECTORS DURING TURBULENT TIMES

Nabeel T. Alsohybel¹ and Nashwan Sabrah²,

¹Sana'a University, Sana'a, Yemen and ²Lebanese International University,
Sana'a, Yemen

ABSTRACT

Scholars have viewed Agile Project Management APM as a prominent solution for software and nonsoftware innovative institutions to cope with its unstable environment. APM has been tested in the software field and proven to be successful. Since 2015, there is ongoing war in Yemen that negatively affects most sectors including the business and microfinance sectors. Social Fund for Development SFD, the microfinance industry leader in Yemen, sought solutions for enhancing the Microfinance Institutions MFIs capabilities during the current environment turbulence. This research investigates any possible advantages in adopting APM in the microfinance sector, out of software domain. A qualitative method was used to conduct the research. three microfinance pioneers were selected and 11 professionals from all management levels were interviewed. In addition, three workshop discussions with 22 members of product development teams were held. The study found that adopting APM would help these MFIs to enhance their resilience by bridging the identified gaps and challenges.

KEYWORDS

Agile Project Management, Traditional Project Management, Product development, Social Fund for Development, New Product Development

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V10N1/10119ijsea04.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] R. G. Cooper, C. J. Easingwood, S. Edgett, E. J. Kleinschmidt, and C. Storey, "[What distinguishes the top performing new products in financial services,](#)" The Journal of Product Innovation Management, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 281–299, 1994.
- [2] S. Cedergren, A. Wall, and C. Norström, "[Evaluation of performance in a product development context,](#)" Business Horizons, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 359–369, 2010.
- [3] K. T. Ulrich and S. D. Eppinger, "[Development Processes and Organizations,](#)" in Product Design and Development, 2011, pp. 11–32.
- [4] A. Wieland and C. Marcus, "[The influence of relational competencies on supply chain resilience: a relational view,](#)" International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 300–320, 2013.
- [5] PMI, "The High Cost of Low Performance: PMI Pulse of Profession," 2014.
- [6] P. Kettunen, "[Agile software development in large-scale new product development organization: team-level perspective,](#)" (Doctoral Dissertation, Helsinki University of Technology), 2009.
- [7] A. F. Sommer, C. Hedegaard, I. Dukovska-Popovska, and K. Steger-Jensen, "[Improved Product Development Performance through Agile/Stage-Gate Hybrids,](#)" Research Technology Management, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 34–44, 2015.
- [8] T. Gustavsson, "[Benefits of Agile Project Management in a Non- Software Development Context – A Literature Review,](#)" Fifth International Scientific Conference on Project Management in the Baltic Countries, no. April 2016.
- [9] R. Cooper, "[Agile – Stage-Gate Hybrids: The Next Stage for Product Development,](#)" ResearchTechnology Management, vol. 6308, no. January, pp. 21–28, 2016.
- [10] N. Ovesen, "The Challenges of Becoming Agile: Implementing and Conducting SCRUM in Integrated Product Development," (Doctoral dissertation, Aalborg University), 2012.
- [11] J. Sutherland and K. Schwaber, "The Scrum Papers: Nuts, Bolts, and Origins of an Agile Process," Scrum inc, 2011.
- [12] The Social Fund for Development, "The Impact of the 2015 Conflict in Yemen on the Local Microfinance Industry," 2015.
- [13] A. S. Alshebami and V. Rengarajan, "[Microfinance Institutions in Yemen ‘Hurdles and Remedies,](#)" International Journal of Social Work, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 10–21, 2017.

- [14] E. H. AboHulaika and V. N. Laturkar, "Microfinance in Yemen: Challenges and Opportunities," *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR)*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 472–481, 2016.
- [15] A. S. Alshebami and M. Kandare, "[Microfinance in Yemen "Challenges and Opportunities](#)","; IJMSS, vol. 2, no. 12, pp. 400–413, 2014.
- [16] A. A. Homaid, A. Y. Zain, Y. A. Al-matari, M. S. Minai, and F. Bin Ahmad, "[The Role of customerfocused strategies to improve islamic microfinance institutions performance: Empirical evidence and lessons from Yemen.](#)" *International Review of Management and marketing*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 291– 299, 2017.
- [17] A. A. Qatinah, "[Factors Affecting Microfinance Demand and Supply Gaps in Yemen.](#)" (Master Thesis, Philipps University of Marburg), 2013.
- [18] N. Jakobi and W. Kinyori, "Understanding National Culture's Influence on Product Innovation Approaches," (Master Thesis, Umea university), 2012.
- [19] E. Conforto, F. Salum, D. C. Amaral, S. L. da Silva, and L. F. M. de Almeida, "Can Agile Project Management Be Adopted by Industries Other than Software Development?" *Project Management Journal*, vol. 45, no. July, pp. 21–34, 2014.
- [20] M. Brand, *The MBP Guide to New Product Development*. ACCION International, 2001.
- [21] CGAP, *Product Development for Microfinance Institutions*. Consultative Group to Assist the Poor CGAP, 2009.
- [22] G. A. N. Wright, M. Brand, Z. Northrip, M. Cohen, M. McCord, and B. Helms, "[Looking Before You Leap: Key Questions That Should Precede Starting New Product Development.](#)" *Journal of Microfinance*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2002.
- [23] A. Jetter and F. Albar, "[Project Management in Product Development: Toward a Framework for Targeted Flexibility.](#)" 2015 Proceedings of PICMET '15: Management of the Technology Age, pp. 1562–1575, 2015.
- [24] R. Cooper, "Perspective: The Stage-Gate idea to launch process – Update, what's new and nexgen systems," *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 213–232, 2008.
- [25] J. Sutherland and N. Ahmad, "[How a Traditional Project Manager Transforms to Scrum: PMBOK vs. Scrum.](#)" Presented paper at Agile 2011, Salt Lake City, pp. 1–7, 2011.
- [26] A. Stare, "[Agile project management in product development projects.](#)" *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 119, pp. 295–304, 2014.

- [27] M. Fowler and J. Highsmith, "[The agile manifesto](#)," *Software Development*, vol. 9, no. August, pp. 28–35, 2001.
- [28] J. Shore and S. Warden, *The Art of Agile Development*, Second edition. Sebastopol: O'Reilly Media, Inc., 2008.
- [29] J. Highsmith, "[Innovative Product Development](#)," in *Agile Project Management: Creating Innovative Products*, 2004, pp. 1–28.
- [30] P. Abrahamsson, J. Warsta, M. T. Siponen, and J. Ronkainen, "[New Directions on Agile Methods: A Comparative Analysis](#)," *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Software Engineering*, pp. 244–254, 2003.
- [31] A. Nasehi, "A quantitative study on critical success factors in agile software development projects; case study IT company," (Master thesis, University of Boras), 2013.
- [32] R. Cooper and A. F. Sommer, "The Agile Stage-Gate Hybrid Model: A Promising New Approach and a New Research Opportunity," *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, vol. 33, no. 5, 2016.
- [33] K. Schwaber and J. Sutherland, "The Scrum Guide," *Scrum.Org and ScrumInc*, no. July, p. 17, 2016. [34] D. K. Rigby, J. Sutherland, and H. Takeuchi, "Embracing agile," *Harvard Business Review*, no. May, pp. 41–50, 2016.
- [35] E. Conforto and D. C. Amaral, "[Agile project management and stage-gate model—A hybrid framework for technology-based companies](#)," *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management - JET-M*, vol. 40, no. 2015, pp. 1–14, 2015.
- [36] A. E. Akgün and H. Keskin, "[Organisational resilience capacity and firm product innovativeness and performance](#)," *International Journal of Production Research*, vol. 52, no. 23, pp. 6918–6937, 2014.
- [37] H. Carvalho, S. Azevedo, and V. Cruz-Machado, "Agile and resilient approaches to supply chain management: influence on performance and competitiveness," *Logistics research*, vol. 4, pp. 49–62, 2012.
- [38] J. McCann, J. Selsky, and J. Lee, "[Building Agility, Resilience and Performance in Turbulent Environments](#)," *People and Strategy*, vol. 32, no. 3, 2009.
- [39] J. W. Creswell, *Qualitative inquiry & research design - Choosing Among Five Approaches*, Second Edi. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, 2007.
- [40] R. K. Yin, *Case study research. Design and Methods*, 5th edition. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, 2014.

- [41] D. R. Cooper and P. S. Schindler, Business research methods, Twelfth edition. McGraw-Hill/Irwin, 2014.
- [42] R. Ørngreen and K. Levinsen, “[Workshops as a Research Methodology](#),” The Electronic Journal of eLearning, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 70–81, 2017.
- [43] M. Brand, “[New Product Development for Microfinance: Evaluation and Preparation Technical Note Number 1](#),” ACCION International, 1998.
- [44] S. Kapoor and G. Sinha, “[Factors influencing new product development in microfinance institutions: A perspective from north Indian microfinance institutions](#),” Journal of Innovation Economics & Management, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 83, 2013.
- [45] R. Cooper and A. F. Sommer, “Agile-Stage-Gate: New idea-to-launch method for manufactured new products is faster, more responsive,” Industrial Marketing Management, 2016.
- [46] M. Cohn, Succeeding with Agile Software Development Using Scrum. Boston: Pearson Education, 2010.
- [47] M. Drury-grogan, “[Performance on Agile Teams: Relating Iteration Objectives and Critical Decisions to Project Management Success factors](#),” Information and Software Technology, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 506–515, 2014.
- [48] T. Vedsmand, S. Kielgast, and R. Cooper, “Integrating Agile with Stage-Gate ® – How New AgileScrum Methods Lead to Faster and Better Innovation,” innovationmanagement.se, pp. 1–15, 2016.

AN ITERATIVE HYBRID AGILE METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING ARCHIVING SYSTEMS

**Khaled Ebrahim Almajed, Walaa Medhat and Tarek El-Shishtawy,
Benha University, Egypt**

ABSTRACT

With the massive growth of the organizations files, the needs for archiving system become a must. A lot of time is consumed in collecting requirements from the organization to build an archiving system. Sometimes the system does not meet the organization needs. This paper proposes a domain-based requirement engineering system that efficiently and effectively develops different archiving systems based on new suggested technique that merges the two best used agile methodologies: extreme programming (XP) and SCRUM. The technique is tested on a real case study. The results shows that the time and effort consumed during analyzing and designing the archiving systems decreased significantly. The proposed methodology also reduces the system errors that may happen at the early stages of the development of the system.

KEYWORDS

Requirement Engineering (RE), Agile, SDLC, Extreme Programming (XP), SCRUM, Archiving.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V10N1/10119ijsea02.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Nuseibeh, B.; Easterbrook, S. [Requirements engineering: a roadmap](#). ICSE'00. Proceedings of the conference on the future of Software engineering. pp. 35–46, 2000.
- [2] Kotonya, Gerald; Sommerville, Ian (September 1998). Requirements Engineering: Processes and Techniques. John Wiley & Sons, 1998.
- [3] Chemuturi, M. (2013). Requirements Engineering and Management for Software Development Projects, 2013.
- [4] Sriram,RandMathew,[S.K Global Software Development Using Agile Methodologies: A Review of Literature](#). 2012 IEEE International Conference on Man- agement of Innovation and Technology, Bali, 2012.
- [5] Medhat, W, Fouad, KM, Yousef, AH, and Moawad, IF, published in 12th international conference of Computer Engineering and Systems (ICCES), 2017
- [6] ManjulGuptaa, Joey F. Georgeb, andWeidongXiaa, “[Relationships between IT department culture and agile software development practices: An empirical investigation](#)”, “International Journal of Information Management44 (2019) 13–24”, 2019.
- [7] Pacheco, C., and Garcia, I. A systematic literature review of stakeholder identification methods in requirements elicitation. Journal of Systems and Software, 85(9), 2171-2181, 2012.
- [8] Amani Mahdi Mohammed, Hisham Mohamed Abushama, “Popular Agile Approaches in Software Development: Review and Analysis”, Researchgate Conference Paper • August 2013.
- [9] Shen, H., Wall, B., Zaremba, M., Chen, Y., & Browne, [J. Integration of business modelling methods for enterprise information system analysis and user requirements gathering](#). Computers in Industry, 54(3), 307-323, 2014.
- [10] Mohammad Almseidin, Khaled Alrfou², Nidal Alnidami³ and Ahmed Tarawneh, “A Comparative Study of Agile Methods: XP versus SCRUM ”, International Journal of Computer Science and Software Engineering (IJCSSE), Volume 4, Issue 5, May 2015
- [11] Khaleel, Y., Abuhamdah, A., Sara, M. A., & Al-Tamimi, B. Components and Analysis Method of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Requirements in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering, 6(2), 682, 2016.

- [12] Farrukh Musa, and Muhammad Ali Tariq, “[Agile Methodology: Hybrid Approach Scrum and XP](#)”, International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 8, Issue 4, April-2017.
- [13] Ankita Sharma, and Manav Bali, “[Comparative Study on Software Development Methods: Agile vs Scrum](#)”, International Journal of Emerging Research in Management & Technology, June 2017.
- [14] Apoorva Singh and Dharendra Pandey, “[Implementation of Requirement Engineering in Extreme Programming and SCRUM](#)”, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science Volume 8, No. 5, May – June 2017.
- [15] Sara Ashraf, Shabib Aftab, “Scrum with the Spices of Agile Family: A Systematic Mapping”, I.J. Modern Education and Computer Science, 2017.
- [16] Julio Cesar Pereira, and Rosaria de F. S. M. Russo, “[Design Thinking Integrated in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review](#)”, “international Conference on Project Management / HCist– International Conference on Health and Social Care Information Systems and Technologies”, 2018.
- [17] Sultania, A. K. (2015, February). Developing software product and test automation software using Agile methodology. In Proceedings of the 2015 Third International Conference on Computer, Communication, Control and Information Technology (C3IT) (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [18] Kniberg, H. (2015). Scrum and XP from the Trenches. Lulu. com.
- [19] Kevin Thompson, Ph.D. “How to Estimate Capacity for Work in Agile Teams”, 2012

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DIFFERENCES IN THE PERCEPTIONS OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (LMS) DESIGN

Yee Mei Lim¹, Aladdin Ayesh² and Keh Niang Chee¹,

¹Tunku Abdul Rahman University College, Malaysia and ²De Montfort University, United Kingdom

ABSTRACT

Learner centred design (LCD) focuses on creating an e-learning system that can fulfil individual needs through personalization, nevertheless there are still many technical challenges. Besides, losing balanced focus on both of the learners and the instructors does not help to create a successful e-learning system. User-centred design helps to improve the usability of a system as it integrates requirements and user interface designs based on users' needs. The findings of this research prove that even the users are provided with the same LMS, not everyone has the same perceptions or tolerance levels of the seven design factors that may cause frustrations to the users, and not everyone has the same satisfaction level of navigation experience and interface design. It is important for the LMS developers to understand that the variations between roles, genders, experiences and ages exist and should not be ignored when designing the system.

KEYWORDS

Learning Management System, Socio-demographics Differences, User-centred Design, User Interface Design, User Satisfaction.

For More Details : <http://aircse.org/journal/ijsea/papers/4513ijsea02.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol4.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Embi, "E-learning in Malaysian higher education institutions: Status, trends, & challenges," 2011.
- [2] R. M. R. Hussain, "E-learning in Higher Education Institutions in Malaysia," *E-mentor*, vol. 5, no. 7, pp. 72–75, 2004.
- [3] H. M. Selim, "Critical success factors for e-learning acceptance: Confirmatory factor models," *Computers and Education*, 2005.
- [4] M. Masrom, O. Zainon, and R. Rahiman, "[Critical success in e-learning: An examination of technological and institutional support factors](#)," *International Journal of Cyber Society and Education Pages*, 2008.
- [5] C. L. Goi and P. Y. Ng, "[E-learning in Malaysia: Success factors in implementing e-learning program](#)," *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 237–246, 2009.
- [6] M. F. Costabile, M. De Marsico, R. Lanzilotti, V. L. Plantamura, and T. Roselli, "[On the Usability Evaluation of E-Learning Applications](#)," in *Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 2005, vol. 1, pp. 1–10.
- [7] C. Abras, D. Maloney-Krichmar, and J. Preece, "User-centered design," *Bainbridge, W. Encyclopedia of Human-Computer Interaction*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 445–456, 2004.
- [8] L. Damodaran, "[User involvement in the systems design process—a practical guide for users](#)," *Behaviour & information technology*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 363–377, 1996.
- [9] F. Klett and P. Pharow, "[How to Achieve User Satisfaction in Complex E-Learning Environments](#)," in *Information Technology Based Higher Education and Training*, 2006. *ITHET '06. 7th International Conference on*, 2006, pp. 773–785.
- [10] P. Zaharias and A. Poylymenakou, "Developing a Usability Evaluation Method for e-Learning Applications : Beyond Functional Usability," *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 75–98, 2009.
- [11] D. Dhar and P. Yammiyavar, "[Design Approach for E-learning Systems: Should it be User Centered or Learner Centered](#)," in *Technology for Education (T4E)*, 2012 *IEEE Fourth International Conference on*, 2012, pp. 239–240.

- [12] T. Carey, K. Harrigan, A. Palmer, and J. Swallow, "[Scaling up a learning technology strategy: supporting student/faculty teams in learner-centred design](#)," Research in Learning Technology, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 15–26, 1999.
- [13] B. Han, X.-W. Hao, and C.-F. Liu, "The design and implementation of user behavior mining in Elearning system," in Automatic Control and Artificial Intelligence (ACAI 2012), International Conference on, 2012, pp. 2078–2081.
- [14] G. Savic and Z. Konjovic, "Learning style based personalization of SCORM e-learning courses," in Intelligent Systems and Informatics, 2009. SISY '09. 7th International Symposium on, 2009, pp. 349–353.
- [15] T. Swinke, "A unique, culture-aware, personalized learning environment," in Interactive Collaborative Learning (ICL), 2012 15th International Conference on, 2012, pp. 1–7.
- [16] R. Zhou and K. Rechert, "[Personalization for Location-Based E-Learning](#)," in Next Generation Mobile Applications, Services and Technologies, 2008. NGMAST '08. The Second International Conference on, 2008, pp. 247–253.
- [17] A. Al-Dujaily and H. Ryu, "[A Study on Personality in Designing Adaptive e-Learning Systems](#)," in Eighth IEEE International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies, 2008. ICALT '08., 2008, pp. 136–138.
- [18] E. Soloway, M. Guzdial, and K. E. Hay, "Learner-centered design: The challenge for HCI in the 21st century," interactions, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 36–48, 1994.
- [19] Q. Gu and T. Sumner, "Support Personalization in Distributed E-Learning Systems through Learner Modeling," in Information and Communication Technologies, 2006. ICTTA '06. 2nd, 2006, vol. 1, pp. 610–615.
- [20] P. Q. Dung and A. M. Florea, "[An Architecture and a Domain Ontology for Personalized Multi-agent e-Learning Systems](#)," in Knowledge and Systems Engineering (KSE), 2011 Third International Conference on, 2011, pp. 181–185.
- [21] M. V. Judy, U. Krishnakumar, and A. G. H. Narayanan, "[Constructing a personalized e-learning system for students with autism based on soft semantic web technologies](#)," in Technology Enhanced Education (ICTEE), 2012 IEEE International Conference on, 2012, pp. 1–5.
- [22] M. K. Khribi, M. Jemni, and O. Nasraoui, "[Automatic Recommendations for E-Learning Personalization Based on Web Usage Mining Techniques and Information Retrieval](#)," in Advanced Learning Technologies, 2008. ICALT '08. Eighth IEEE International Conference on, 2008, pp. 241–245.

- [23] N. Pandey, S. Sahu, R. K. Tyagi, and A. Dwivedi, "Learning algorithms For intelligent agents based e-learning system," in Advance Computing Conference (IACC), 2013 IEEE 3rd International, 2013, pp. 1034–1039.
- [24] L. Zhuhadar, E. Romero, and R. Wyatt, "The Effectiveness of Personalization in Delivering Elearning Classes," in Advances in Computer-Human Interactions, 2009. ACHI '09. Second International Conferences on, 2009, pp. 130–135.
- [25] P.-C. Sun, R. J. Tsai, G. Finger, Y.-Y. Chen, and D. Yeh, "[What drives a successful e-Learning? An empirical investigation of the critical factors influencing learner satisfaction](#)," Computers & Education, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 1183–1202, 2008.
- [26] M. P. Penna, V. Stara, and M. De Rose, "The failure of e-learning: why should we use a learner centred design," Journal of e-Learning and Knowledge Society, vol. 3, no. 2, 2009.
- [27] N. Avouris, N. Tselios, C. Fidas, and E. Papachristos, "[Website evaluation: A usability-based perspective](#)," in Advances in Informatics, Springer, 2003, pp. 217–231.
- [28] J. Tidwell, Designing Interfaces, 2nd ed. Sebastopol: O'Reilly Media, 2011.
- [29] A. Edmundson, Globalized e-learning cultural challenges. IGI Global, 2007.
- [30] S. Downey, R. M. Wentling, T. Wentling, and A. Wadsworth, "[The relationship between national culture and the usability of an e-learning system](#)," Human Resource Development International, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 47–64, 2005.
- [31] P. Lea, "Understanding the culture of e-learning," Industrial and Commercial Training, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 217–219, 2003.
- [32] D. Gefen and D. W. Straub, "[Gender differences in the perception and use of e-mail: An extension to the technology acceptance model](#)," MIS quarterly, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 389–400, Dec. 1997.
- [33] T. Lindberg, R. Näsänen, and K. Müller, "How age affects the speed of perception of computer icons," Displays, vol. 27, no. 4-5, pp. 170–177, 2006.
- [34] J. Lazar, K. Bessiere, I. Ceaparu, J. Robinson, and B. Shneiderman, "Help! I'm Lost: User Frustration in Web Navigation," Web Navigation, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 18–26, 2003.
- [35] N. Bevan, "[Encyclopaedia of Human Computer Interaction](#)," in Encyclopedia of human computer interaction, C. Ghaoui, Ed. Idea Group Inc (IGI), 2006, pp. 362–372.
- [36] L. L. Lohr, "Designing the instructional interface," in Computers in Human Behavior, 2000, vol. 16, pp. 161–182.

- [37] C. Bee and R. Madrigal, "[Outcomes are in the eye of the beholder: The influence of affective dispositions on disconfirmation emotions, outcome satisfaction, and enjoyment](#)," *Journal of Media Psychology: Theories, Methods, and Applications*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 143–153, 2012.
- [38] U. R. Hülshager, H. J. E. M. Alberts, A. Feinholdt, and J. W. B. Lang, "[Benefits of Mindfulness at Work: The Role of Mindfulness in Emotion Regulation, Emotional Exhaustion, and Job Satisfaction](#)," *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 98, no. 2, pp. 310–325, Mar. 2012.
- [39] T. Browne, R. Hewitt, M. Jenkins, and R. Walker, "2008 survey of Technology Enhanced Learning For Higher Education in the UK." pp. 1–58, 2008.
- [40] S. Murugesan, "[Web application development: Challenges and the role of web engineering](#)," in *Web engineering: modelling and implementing web applications*, G. Rossi, Ed. Springer, 2008, pp. 7–32.
- [41] S. E. Lakhan and K. Jhunjhunwala, "Open Source Software in Education," *EDUCAUSE Quarterly Magazine*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 32–40, 2008.
- [42] B. Shneiderman, C. Plaisant, M. Cohen, and S. Jacobs, [Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human Computer Interaction](#), 5th ed. Boston, MA: Addison-Wesley, 2005.
- [43] M. Jenkins, T. Browne, and R. Walker, "A longitudinal perspective between March 2001, March 2003 and March 2005 for higher education in the United Kingdom," 2005.
- [44] Y. Guo, D. Qian, J. Guan, and J. Wang, "Usability testing on a government training platform: A case study," in *2010 2nd International Conference on Education Technology and Computer (ICETC)*, 2010, vol. 2, pp. 2–214.
- [45] A. Granic and V. Glavinic, "[Evaluation of interaction design in web-based intelligent tutoring systems](#)," in *28th International Conference on Information Technology Interfaces*, 2006.
- [46] B. L. Capehart and T. Middelkoop, *Handbook of Web Based Energy Information and Control Systems*. Fairmont Pr, 2011.
- [47] J. Nielsen, "Top 10 Mistakes in Web Design," vol. 2011, no. August. 2011.
- [48] L. Triacca, D. Bolchini, L. Botturi, and A. Inversini, "[MiLE: Systematic Usability Evaluation for Elearning Web Applications](#)," *Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education*, vol. 12, no. 4, 2004.

- [49] M. Levene, *An Introduction to Search Engines and Web Navigation*, 2nd ed. John Wiley & Sons, 2010.
- [50] P. Bradford, M. Porciello, N. Balkon, and D. Backus, “[The blackboard learning system: the be all and end all in educational instruction?](#),” *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 301–314, 2007.
- [51] S. J. Coopman, “A critical examination of Blackboard’s e-learning environment,” *First Monday*, vol. 14, no. 6–1 June 2009, 2009.
- [52] N. A. Weiss, *Elementary Statistics*, 6th ed. Addison-Wesley, 2004.
- [53] D. C. Montgomery, *Design and Analysis of Experiments*. John Wiley & Sons Singapore, 2013

DETECTION AND REFACTORING OF BAD SMELL CAUSED BY LARGE SCALE

Jiang Dexun, Ma Peijun, Su Xiaohong and Wang Tiantian,

Harbin Institute of Technology, China

ABSTRACT

Bad smells are signs of potential problems in code. Detecting bad smells, however, remains time consuming for software engineers despite proposals on bad smell detection and refactoring tools. Large Class is a kind of bad smells caused by large scale, and the detection is hard to achieve automatically. In this paper, a Large Class bad smell detection approach based on class length distribution model and cohesion metrics is proposed. In programs, the lengths of classes are confirmed according to the certain distributions. The class length distribution model is generalized to detect programs after grouping. Meanwhile, cohesion metrics are analyzed for bad smell detection. The bad smell detection experiments of open source programs show that Large Class bad smell can be detected effectively and accurately with this approach, and refactoring scheme can be proposed for design quality improvements of programs.

KEYWORDS

Distribution rule; Class length distribution model; Cohesion metrics; Bad smell detection; refactoring scheme.

For More Details : <http://aircse.org/journal/ijsea/papers/4513ijsea01.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijsea/vol4.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Fowler, (1999) "Refactoring: Improving the design of existing code", Addison-Wesley, pp89-92.
- [2] B.F. Webster, (1995) "Pitfalls of Object Oriented Development", first M&T Books, Feb.
- [3] A.J. Riel, (1996) "Object-Oriented Design Heuristics", Addison-Wesley.
- [4] G. Travassos, F. Shull, M. Fredericks, & V.R. Basili., (1999) "[Detecting Defects in Object-Oriented Designs: Using Reading Techniques to Increase Software Quality](#)", Proceeding of 14th Conference in Object-Oriented Programming, Systems, Languages, and Applications, pp47-56.
- [5] R. Marinescu, (2004) "[Detection Strategies: Metrics-Based Rules for Detecting Design Flaws](#)", Proceeding of 20th International Conference in Software Maintenance, pp350-359.
- [6] Ladan Tahvildari & Kostas Kontogiannis, (2003) "[A Metric-Based Approach to Enhance Design Quality through Meta-Pattern Transformations](#)", 7th European Conference Software Maintenance and Reengineering, pp183-192.
- [7] M. O'Keefe & M. O'Conneide, (2008) "Search-based refactoring: an empirical study", Journal of software maintenance and evolution: research and practice, pp345-364.
- [8] K. Dhambri, H. Sahraoui & P. Poulin, (2008) "Visual Detection of Design Anomalies", Proceeding of 12th European Conference in Software Maintenance and Reeng, pp279-283.
- [9] G. Langelier, H.A. Sahraoui & P. Poulin, (2005) "[Visualization-Based Analysis of Quality for LargeScale Software Systems](#)", Proceeding of 20th International Conference in Automated Software Engineering , pp214-223.
- [10] M. Lanza & R. Marinescu, (2006) "[Object-Oriented Metrics in Practice](#)", Springer-Verlag. pp125- 128.
- [11] E. van Emden & L. Moonen, (2002) "[Java Quality Assurance by Detecting Code Smells](#)", Proceeding of 9th Working Conference in Reverse Engineering, pp120-128.
- [12] F. Simon, F. Steinbruckner C. Lewerentz, (2001) "[Metrics Based Refactoring](#)", Proceeding of 5th European Conference in Software Maintenance and Reengineering, pp30-38.

- [13] D.X. Jiang & P.J. Ma, (2012) “[Detecting Bad Smells With Weight Based Distance Metrics Theory](#)”, Proceeding of 2nd International Conference on Instrumentation, Measurement, Computer, Communication and Control, pp299-304.
- [14] H. Liu, Z.Y. Ma & W.Z. Shao, (2012) “[Schedule of Bad Smell Detection and Resolution: A New Way to Save Effort](#)”, IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, Vol. 38, No. 1, pp220-235.
- [15] D. Fontana, A. Francesca & P.Braione, (2012) “[Automatic detection of bad smells in code An experimental assessment](#)”, Journal of Object Technology, Vol. 11, No. 2, pp1-38.
- [16] <http://pmd.sourceforge.net>.
- [17] <http://checkstyle.sourceforge.net>.
- [18] J.W. Han & M. Kamber, (2005) “Data Mining Concepts and Techniques”, Morgan Kaufmann Publishers.